

SZ-SB-I-09 Searching for information about a teacher studies course in music (English)

Author	@Sönke Erdmann ; @Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Julia Lehmler ; @Ricarda Peil ; @Alexander Schröter ; @Tara-Marie Endries (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
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Title	Searching for information about a teacher studies course in music
Educational area	#school #higher-education
Persona	P: Greta - Pupil https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091323
Short description	Greta, a prospective music teacher, uses BIRD to find out about studying and applying to universities. Her research focuses on aptitude tests.
Result	Greta knows the dates and requirements for the necessary aptitude tests.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario• Process "Research"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Greta is registered at BIRD• Greta is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #workspace #data-wallet
Services / tools	#video-conference #texteditor

Problem scenario

Introduction

Greta Pulka will graduate from high school soon. Immediately afterwards, she wants to study music to become a teacher. Therefore, she is already trying to find a suitable university and gather comprehensive information about the requirements for the program.

Problem definition

Greta knows what she wants to study, but she doesn't yet know exactly which university to attend. She already has a list of universities that offer suitable courses, but she would like to gather more information. She might need specific documents or sufficient lead

time for the application or entrance exams, and she doesn't want to miss out on things simply because she didn't research them in time.

Background and context

Greta has compiled a list of suitable universities that she is currently reviewing. She wants to make the right decision and prepare well for the application process and the start of her studies. For this reason, it is important for Greta to gather as much information as possible and to weigh her options carefully. Greta makes pro and con lists for everything.

Greta knows that you can't just enroll in a teacher training program, especially for music. She also knows that there will probably be many applicants. The admission requirements vary between different universities because each university can set them independently. Greta doesn't know what to pay attention to; This is her first time applying to a university, and she is not familiar with the formalities.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Time is running out. Greta doesn't want to miss any deadlines and wants to gather all the necessary information before making a decision or narrowing down her options. Greta struggles with uncertainty, which is why it is important for her to invest time in gathering information. However, she doesn't want to chase the information she needs if there are alternatives that could make things easier for her.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Researching online is very time-consuming. Greta would have to look at each university's website individually and search for the information she needs. Unfortunately, every university website is structured differently and the information is often spread across various subpages, so that at the end of a lengthy research process, Greta still doesn't know if she really has all the information she needs.

Activity scenario

Process "Research"

Step 1: Greta opens the LearningPathFinder in BIRD to search for information on the application process, course content, and study schedule for music teacher training at different universities. As an musically trained prospective student, Greta has already compiled a list of potential universities in BIRD that she would like to take a closer look at.

Step 2: In the LearningPathFinder, she first completes the search by entering the

following keywords: “application process”, “study process” and “music teaching degree”. Greta also sets the “federal state” filter to her home state of Brandenburg and neighboring states (like Berlin), as she doesn't want to move too far from her family. She also agrees to data sharing for this search query, allowing information stored in her Data Wallet to be used. She is then presented with a summary of the entries she used in her search and has the option to save her query for later.

Step 3: On the results page, Greta finds will find the website “Become a music teacher” from the Federal Association of Music Education (BMU), where all information about the application process and the universities that offer the course is collected: [Information about the profession of musician](#).

Step 4: Greta subscribes to the results page and follows the link to the external website.

Step 5: Once on the website, she finds universities in the surrounding states that she hadn't known about before and therefore weren't on her list. She adds a few after briefly looking at their profiles.

Step 6: Greta opens the workspace in BIRD and creates a project called “Music Education”. She drags and drops a text editing tool into the new project, transfers her existing list, and imports information from the BMU website. Her project also contains individual documents with the names of various universities, which she can tag accordingly.

Step 7: Greta can also find all the dates for the aptitude tests of the various universities on the BMU website. To keep track of them, she adds the calendar tool to her “Music Teaching” project and creates events for each exam that is relevant to her. For each date, she notes factors like distance, whether she likes the university, etc., and marks them with a “plus” or “minus”. When Greta opens an appointment, she has direct access to the documents because they are linked.

Step 8: Greta records specific requirements and contact information for the study program coordinators in the individual documents for each university.

Step 9: She noticed on the university websites that the dates were scattered and not always easy to find, leaving her without detailed information. That's why she's glad she has her own overview. The university websites are sometimes complex, and Greta can't find what she's looking for directly, so she opens the BIRD again to search for more information about the “music teaching aptitude test”.

Step 10: Greta applies the “federal state” filter to her federal state and neighboring states, as she specifically wants to find out about the aptitude tests of the universities on her list.

Step 11: Greta finds what she's looking for in the results list of the LearningPathFinder, in addition to the aptitude test criteria, she is also shown relevant information events, including dial-in details.. Greta saves this information.

Step 12: That same evening, a digital information session on music education is taking place at the University of Potsdam. Potsdam is one of the universities that are on her list. Greta logs into the video conferencing tool and joins the session. She follows the lecture and the Q&A session while simultaneously taking notes on the course in her personal workspace.